

How Does Innovative Behavior Mediating The Effect of Visionary Leadership, Learning Organization and Creativity On Lecturers' Performance?

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 06, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Visionary Leadership, Learning Organization, Creativity, Innovative Behavior, Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6419823</p>	<p><i>The study aims is not only to explore the empirical effect of visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work on lecturers' performance but also to prove the theoretical model regarding innovative behavior as a mediator of visionary leadership, learning organization, and creativity on lecturers' performance. This research uses a quantitative survey method through a Likert scale model questionnaire. The research participants are comprised of 124 lecturers taken proportionally from 179 lecturers of 17 Midwifery universities in Banten Province, Indonesia. Data analysis uses path analysis supported by descriptive statistics, correlational matrices, and SITOREM. The research results indicate that visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work significantly affect lecturers' performance. Besides, innovative behavior also indirectly mediates the effect of visionary leadership, learning organization, and creativity on lecturers' performance. Thus, a new model regarding the effect of visionary leadership, learning organization, and creativity on lecturers' performance, mediated by innovative work, was confirmed. The research suggested that the lecturers' performance can improve through visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work. Therefore, researchers and practitioners can adopt a new empirical model to enhance lecturers' performance through visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work in the future.</i></p>

Introduction

The quality of Indonesia's human resources has not shown a significant advantage. The indication is that Indonesia's Human Development Index in 2020 is still ranked 111 out of 189 countries in the world. This condition is caused, among others, by universities that have not been able to produce high-quality human resource output. As an illustration, none of the 17 Midwifery Universities has an "A" accreditation. It was noted that 15 midwifery universities were accredited "B", and two midwifery universities were accredited "C". These empirical facts indicate that midwifery universities in Banten Province have not been able to show optimal higher education performance. This reflects that the performance of lecturers as the main actors in implementing higher education has not been maximized, both in teaching, research, community service, scientific publications, and support.

Performance refers to the level of achievement of an employee's duties (Rue et al., 2016). In addition, performance is also a set of employee behaviors that contribute, both positively and negatively, to the achievement of organizational goals (Colquitt et al., 2019). Colquitt et al identified three performance indicators. First, task performance, which is a series of obligations that must be fulfilled by employees to get compensation from continuous work. Second, citizenship behavior, as a contribution to positive behavior, namely employee voluntary activities that can be appreciated or not, but make a positive contribution to the organization and to improve the quality of work. Third, counter-productive, namely behavior that contributes negatively, for example ownership deviations, production deviations in the form of waste of resources and material abuse, political deviations, and individual attacks in the form of disturbances and attacks. Aguinis (2014) also argues similarly that performance includes two behaviors. First, task performance, namely: activities that transform raw materials into goods or services produced by the organization and activities that assist the transformation process by replenishing the supply of raw materials, distributing finished products, or providing important planning, coordination, supervision, or staff functions that enable the organization to function effectively and efficiently. Second, contextual performance, namely behavior that contributes to organizational effectiveness by providing a good environment in which task performance can take place. In the context of the implementation of higher education, lecturer performance is related to the three obligations of higher education which includes: teaching, research, community service, scientific publications, and support (Purwanto, 2015; Yanuarita, 2016;

Brodjonegoro, 2008). This means that teaching, research, community service, scientific publications, and support are important indicators that determine the quality of universities. Therefore, the research aims to explore the performance of lecturers through the perspective of visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work.

Visionary Leadership and Lecturer Performance

Several previous studies have shown that performance is influenced by visionary leadership (Kantabutra, 2006; Ali et al., 2019; Esfarjani et al., 2020; Setyaningsih et al., 2020; Widodo & Yusuf, 2021). It shows that visionary leadership is an essential determinant of performance. Visionary leadership is very important for organizations, so visionary leadership is referred to as a quality that transcends institutions (Widodo & Chandrawaty, 2021). Robbins and Coulter (2016) state that visionary leadership is the ability to create and articulate realistic, credible, and interesting visions of the future that can improve current circumstances. For Siswanti and Rahatmawati (2014), visionary leadership refers to a leadership pattern that is intended to give meaning to the work and efforts that need to be carried out together by organizational members by giving direction and meaning to the work and efforts carried out based on a clear vision. In comparison, Goleman et al. (2006) stated that visionary leadership is a leadership pattern that seeks to move people towards a shared dream with the most positive emotional climate impact and is most appropriate when change requires a new vision or when a clear direction is needed. Chen (2019) explained that visionary leadership pays attention to setting direction, encouraging change, being an organizational coach, and being able to provide an explanation of the organizations' vision both internally and externally. According to Kadir et al. (2020), visionary leadership describes how to intellectually manage problems and empower subordinates to develop and implement new ideas to achieve the goals and objectives that have been set. Visionary leadership can be measured through indicators: futuristic outlook, clarity of articulating a vision, encouragement to members to achieve goals, direction to achieve success, and taking risks with careful calculations (Effendi, 2015; Robbins & Coulter, 2016; Siswanti & Rahatmawati 2014; Hidayat & Machali, 2010; Anshar 2017; Widodo & Chandrawaty, 2021). For example, university, faculty, or study program leaders who proactively encourage lecturers to achieve goals, direct lecturers to achieve success, and provide flexibility for lecturers to carry out risky experiments can stimulate lecturers to be more intense and dedicated to carrying out teaching assignments, research, and scientific publications as well as community service. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated (H):

H₁: Visionary leadership has a direct effect on lecturers' performance.

Learning Organization and Lecturers' Performance

Performance is also influenced by learning organization (Aziz et al., 2018; Karim & Rahman, 2018; Khunsoonthornkit & Panjakajornsakm, 2018; Suifan & Allouzi, 2018). This indicates that learning organization is an important antecedent for performance. According to Peter Senge (in Yaşlıoğlu et al., 2014), learning organizations are institutions where people continually develop capacities, creating highly desirable outcomes, organizations where new and expansive patterns of thinking are fostered, collective aspirations are freed, and people are constantly learning how to learn. For Marsick and Watkins (2003), a learning organization is an organization whose members are continuously learning with their capacity to change. Meanwhile, Robbins and Coulter (2016: 350) state that a learning organization is an organization that has developed its capacity to continue to learn, adapt and change. A learning organization is also an organization that develops capacity on an ongoing basis to adapt and change (Robbins & Judge, 2015), an organization that intentionally designs and develops its structure, culture, and strategy to enhance and maximize the exploratory and exploitative potential of organizational learning (Jones, 2013), and a lifelong learning culture where members continuously learn something new (Noe et al., 2015). Moreover, learning organizations can also be described as organizations that are successful in creating, acquiring, and transferring knowledge and modifying behavior to reflect new knowledge. Learning organizations emphasize systematic problem solving, experimenting with new ideas, learning from past experiences and histories, and from the experiences of others, and transferring knowledge quickly throughout the organization (Certo & Certo, 2009). Learning organization can be measured through indicators: commitment to learning all the time, openness to change, problem-solving approach, member participation in formulating and implementing the organizational vision, use of organizational facilities to collaborate in learning, and comprehensive way of thinking in solving problems (Noe et al., 2015; Tjakraatmadja & Lantu, 2006; Beardwell & Thompson, 2017; Widodo & Gunawan, 2020; Robbins & Coulter, 2016). As an illustration, university leaders who are committed to learning all the time, are open to change, oriented to problem-solving approaches, involve lecturers in formulating and implementing the university's vision, encourage the use of campus facilities to collaborate in learning, and encourage a comprehensive way of thinking in solving problems will tend to stimulate lecturers to carry out teaching assignments, research and scientific publications, as well as better community service. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated (H):

H₂: Learning organization has a direct effect on lecturers' performance.

Creativity and Lecturers' Performance

Performance can also be affected by creativity. Investigating by researchers, for example, Chandrasekara and Kappagoda (2019), Kaveski and Beuren (2020), Soegiastuti and Muchayatin (2020), and Nur et al. (2021) indicated that creativity had a significant effect on performance. According to Colquitt et al. (2019), employee creativity is necessary to spark the types of innovations that enable organizations to stay ahead of their competition. Because creative ideas do not always get implemented, it is important to recognize creative performance behaviors, as well as the creative outcomes that result from those behaviors. Creativity is the use of imagination or original ideas to create something (Bessant & Tidd, 2018). Asbari et al. (2021) view individual creativity as a persons' efforts in generating new things, useful ideas, or solutions to solve problems. Individual creativity refers to the process of creating ideas or solving problems and actual ideas or solutions. Individual creativity describes individuals' cognitive processes thinking and potentially related activities. For Soegiastuti and Muchayatin (2020), creativity is an initiative to produce useful, correct, appropriate, and valuable products or processes for more heuristic tasks, namely something that is an incomplete guide, guide, or guide that will lead him to understand, learn, or discover something new. Meanwhile, according to Nabil et al. (2017), creativity is creating valuable and useful new products, services, ideas, procedures, or processes by individuals working in complex social organizations.

McKenna (2020) states that creativity is the development of new ideas. Creativity has a lot to do with individual characteristics. Creative people have intelligence and personality characteristics such as being open, more flexible, and willing to use various ways of looking at problems. Creativity can be measured by indicators: the novelty of perspective in seeing situations, originality of ideas, fluency in generating ideas, flexibility in developing ideas, and completeness in developing ideas (Bessant & Tid, 2018; McShane & Von Glinow, 2018; Widodo 2021; McKenna, 2020). For example, lecturers who have a novel perspective in seeing situations, originality of ideas, fluency in generating ideas, and flexibility in developing ideas will tend to encourage lecturers to carry out teaching assignments, research, and scientific publications, as well as community service to be more creative so as to produce new things that are interesting indispensable for the development of science and civilization. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated (H):

H₃: Creativity has a direct effect on lecturers' performance.

Innovative Behavior and Lecturers' Performance

Performance can also be stimulated by innovative behavior. This can be seen, for example, from the findings of Gunday et al. (2011), Marques and Ferreira (2009), Shanker et al. (2017), Schuh et al. (2018), and Rizki et al. (2019), which shows that innovative behavior affects performance. Innovative behavior is an individual action that is directed to produce, introduce or apply new findings that are beneficial at every level of the organization. These new findings include the development of new product ideas or technologies, changing administrative procedures aimed at improving working relationships, or applying new ideas or technologies to work processes aimed at significantly increasing efficiency and effectiveness (Kleysen & Street, 2001). Innovative behavior is also an acceptable multi-stage process involving idea formation, coalition development, and implementation (Leong & Rasli, 2014). In the work context, innovative behavior is a series of stages of work activities in developing and improving effective work behavior (Soebardi, 2012). Yuan and Woodman (2010) say that the concept of innovative work behavior combines reasoning with alternative ways, constantly looking for progress, looking for new ways to complete tasks, looking for new technologies, implementing different work strategies and methods, and ensuring resources so that new ideas can be developed can come true. According to Tastana and Davoudib (2015), innovative work behavior is a behavioral approach and describes it in a broader framework that includes social, organizational, motivational, and psychological processes to produce innovative employee behavior. Meanwhile, according to Cingoza and Akdo (2011), innovative work behavior is related to efforts to produce something that intentionally promotes and realizes new ideas in work roles, workgroups, or organizations to get benefits for roles in workgroups or organizations. In addition, innovative work behavior reflects a multi-stage process in which a person recognizes his problems in which he generates new ideas and solutions (new or adopted), works to promote and build support for them and produces prototypes or models that can be applied for use and development benefits of the organization or its part (Al-Shammari, 2019). Innovative behavior can be measured by indicators: an exploration of new ideas, development of new ideas, promotion of new ideas, implementation of the results of developing ideas, and changes that benefit the organization. If in adequate condition, the indicators can encourage the improvement of lecturer performance (Alshammari, 2019; Tastana & Davoudib, 2015; Cingoza & Akdo, 2011; Leong & Rasli, 2014; Koziol-Nadolna, 2020). For example, lecturers who actively explore new ideas, develop new ideas, promote new ideas, and apply the results of idea development can encourage lecturers to carry out teaching assignments, research, and scientific publications, as well as community service with new outputs that are very much needed by universities in developing science and technology. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated (H):

H₄: Innovative behavior has a direct effect on lecturers' performance.

Visionary Leadership and Innovative Behavior

Innovative behavior is not only influenced by performance; it is also influenced by visionary leadership. Previous studies by Naqvi et al. (2017), Van der Voet and Steijn (2020), and Kadir et al. (2020) claimed that visionary leadership influenced innovative behavior. This shows that university leadership which is characterized by a futuristic outlook, clearly articulated vision, encouragement to members to achieve goals, direction to achieve success, and careful risk taking can increase the innovative behavior of lecturers which is reflected in the exploration of new ideas, the development of new ideas, promotion of new ideas, implementation of the results of developing ideas, and changes that benefit the organization. For example, the leadership of a university, faculty, or study program that puts forward a futuristic view, proactively encourages lecturers to achieve goals, and intensely directs lecturers to achieve success will tend to stimulate lecturers to show innovative behavior through exploration of new ideas, development of new ideas, promotion of new ideas, and implementation of the results of developing ideas, which can bring about positive changes in the university organization. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated (H):

H₅: Visionary leadership has a direct effect on lecturers' innovative behavior.

Learning Organization and Innovative Behavior

Innovative behavior is also influenced by learning organizations. Research results conducted by Park et al. (2016), Anwar and Niode (2017), Chen et al. (2018), and Allouzi et al. (2018) show that learning organizations are related to innovative behavior. It confirms that a learning organization is reflected in a commitment to learning over time, openness to change, problem-solving approach, participation of members in formulating and implementing the organizations' vision, use of organizational facilities to collaborate in learning, and a comprehensive way of thinking in solving problems crucial to behavior. Innovative lecturers manifested in the exploration of new ideas, the development of new ideas, the promotion of new ideas, the application of the results of the development of ideas, and changes that benefit the organization. For example, university leaders who have a commitment to learning all the time, are open to change, are problem-solving oriented, encourage the use of campus facilities to collaborate in learning, and encourage a comprehensive way of thinking in solving problems will tend to stimulate lecturers to show innovative behavior in the form of exploring, , develop, promote and implement new ideas that are beneficial to the university. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated (H):

H₆: Learning organization has a direct effect on lecturers' innovative behavior.

Creativity and Innovative Behavior

Innovative behavior is also influenced by creativity. Scholars proved that creativity is related to innovative behavior (Shon & Jung, 2010; Slåtten, 2014; Stojčić et al., 2018; Suendarti et al., 2020; Widodo & Gustari, 2020). It indicates that creativity is a predisposition for innovative behavior. That is, creativity reflected in the novelty of perspective in seeing situations, originality of ideas, fluency in generating ideas, flexibility in developing ideas, and completeness in developing ideas has the potential to increase lecturers' innovative behavior, which is manifested in exploring new ideas, developing new ideas, promoting new ideas, implementing results of idea development, and changes that benefit the organization. As an illustration, lecturers who have a novel perspective in seeing situations, originality of ideas, fluency in generating ideas, and flexibility in developing ideas can stimulate their innovative behavior through exploration, development, promotion, and application of new ideas that are beneficial for themselves and the university. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated (H):

H₇: Creativity has a direct effect on lecturers' innovative behavior.

Methods

This research uses a quantitative approach to the survey method through a questionnaire in the form of a Likert scale model with five option answers: strongly disagree (score= 1), disagree (score= 2), neutral (score= 3), agree (score= 4), and strongly agree (score= 5) to verify the hypotheses (Hair et al., 2018). The questionnaire is designed by researchers themselves based on the theoretical indicators from the experts. The visionary leadership questionnaire consists of 35 items with a corrected item-total correlation coefficient = .53 – .94 and an alpha coefficient = .99. Learning organization consists of 34 items with a corrected item-total correlation coefficient = .63 – .91 and an alpha coefficient = .98. Creativity consists of 36 items with a corrected item-total correlation coefficient = .45 – .91 and an alpha coefficient = .98. Innovative behavior consists of 37 items with a corrected item-total correlation coefficient = .36 – .94 and an alpha coefficient = .97. Lecturer performance consists of 37 items with a corrected item-total correlation coefficient = .41 – .88 and an alpha coefficient = .97. All variables have a corrected item-total correlation coefficient > .361 and a coefficient of alpha > .7, so it is valid and reliable as a research instrument (Van Griethuijsen et al., 2014; Hair et al., 2018). This research

participant is 124 lecturers taken proportionally from 179 lecturers of 17 Midwifery universities in Banten Province, Indonesia, based on the Yamane formula with 5% precision.

Data were analyzed using path analysis and SITOREM (scientific identification theory to conduct operation research in education management) (Hardhienata, 2017), supported by descriptive statistics and correlations. The significance of the direct effect was determined using the T-test and the indirect effect using the Sobel test (Z) (Abu-Bader & Jones, 2021). Descriptive, correlational, and path analyses were performed by the SPSS Version 26.

Result and Discussion

Result

The descriptive statistical analysis and correlations of the five research variables are present in Table 1. The mean values of the five variables from the lowest to the highest in succession are creativity (111.40), visionary leadership (113.53), innovative behavior (116.71), learning organization (118.60), and lecturer performance (122.86). Meanwhile, the standard deviation values of the five variables from the lowest to the highest in succession are creativity (27.488), lecturer performance (30.025), innovative behavior (30.447), learning organization (31.343), and visionary leadership (32.406). The correlation analysis results in all variables have significant relationships with the other variables at level $p < .01$. This condition indicates that all the variables have a mutual relationship with each other. The correlation coefficients from the lowest to the highest in succession are learning organization and lecturer performance (.783), visionary leadership and lecturer performance (.812), innovative behavior and lecturer performance (.826), visionary leadership and innovative behavior (.837), visionary leadership and creativity (.839), learning organization and innovative behavior (.841), learning organization and creativity (.848), creativity and lecturer performance (.850), visionary leadership and learning organization (.889), and creativity and innovative behavior (.937).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics and Correlational Matrix of Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4	5
1. Visionary leadership	113.53	32.406	1.00				
2. Learning organization	118.60	31.343	.889**	1.00			
3. Creativity	111.40	27.488	.839**	.848**	1.00		
4. Innovative behavior	116.71	30.447	.837**	.841**	.937**	1.00	
5. Lecturer performance	122.86	30.025	.812**	.783**	.850**	.826**	1.00

** $p < .01$

The results of hypothesis testing with path analysis regarding the effects of visionary leadership, learning organization, and creativity on lecturer performance, mediated by innovative behavior, are summarized in Table 2 and visualized in Figure 1. All the hypotheses were supported (t/Z value $> t/Z$ table at $\alpha = .01$). In detail, visionary leadership has a significant direct effect on lecturer performance ($\gamma = .812$, $p < .01$), learning organization has a significant direct effect on lecturer performance ($\gamma = .784$, $p < .01$), creativity has a significant direct effect on lecturer performance ($\gamma = .851$, $p < .01$). Innovative behavior has a significant direct effect on lecturer performance ($\beta = .827$, $p < .01$). Besides, visionary leadership has a significant direct effect on innovative behavior ($\gamma = .838$, $p < .01$), learning organization has a significant direct effect on innovative behavior ($\gamma = .841$, $p < .01$). Creativity has a significant direct effect on innovative behavior ($\gamma = .937$, $p < .01$). In addition, Visionary leadership has an indirect effect on lecturer performance, mediated by innovative behavior ($\beta = .693$, $p < .01$), learning organization has an indirect effect on lecturer performance, mediated by innovative behavior ($\beta = .696$, $p < .01$), and creativity has an indirect effect on lecturer performance, mediated by innovative behavior ($\beta = .774$, $p < .01$).

Table 2. Hypothesis Testing

Direct and Indirect Effect	Path Coefficient	t Value	Decision
H ₁ : Visionary leadership on lecturer performance	.812**	15.348	Supported
H ₂ : Learning organization on lecturer performance	.784**	13.943	Supported

H ₃ : Creativity on lecturer performance	.851**	17.889	Supported
H ₄ : Innovative behavior on lecturer performance	.827**	16.224	Supported
H ₅ : Visionary leadership on innovative behavior	.838**	16.949	Supported
H ₆ : Learning organization on innovative behavior	.841**	17.117	Supported
H ₇ : Creativity on innovative behavior	.937**	29.699	Supported

** p < .01

Figure 1. Path Coefficients & T Values

In Table 3, the indirect effect of visionary leadership, learning organization, and creativity on lecturer performance, mediated by innovative behavior, was significant. Visionary leadership had a significant effect on lecturer performance, mediated by innovative behavior ($\beta = .693, p < .01$). Learning organization had a significant effect on lecturer performance, mediated by innovative behavior ($\beta = .696, p < .01$). Creativity had a significant effect on lecturer performance, mediated by innovative behavior ($\beta = .774, p < .01$).

Table 3. Indirect Effect Testing

Direct and Indirect Effect	Path Coefficient	Z Value	Decision
1. Visionary leadership on lecturer performance mediated by innovative behavior	.693**	11.80	Supported
2. Learning organization on lecturer performance mediated by innovative behavior	.696**	11.78	Supported
3. Creativity on lecturer performance mediated by innovative behavior	.774**	14.28	Supported

** p < .01

The recapitulation of SITOREM analysis results to determine the priority scale of indicators that need to be maintained and developed as well as indicators that need to be improved is presented in Figure 2. The criteria for determining the classification of indicators for each variable are 4.00 – 5.00 need to be maintained or developed, while 0.00 – 3.99 need improvement (Hardhienata, 2017). That means, if indicator value (IV) ≥ 4.00 is need to be maintained or developed, meanwhile < 4.00 is need improvement.

Table 4. Recapitulation of SITOREM Analysis Results

Performance			
Indicator in Initial State	Indicator after Weighting by Expert	IV	
1 Teaching	1 st Scientific publications (25.37%)	2.75	
2 Research	2 nd Research (23.88%)	3.00	
3 Community service	3 rd Teaching (19.41%)	4.26	

4	Scientific publications	4 th	Community service (17.91%)	3.22
5	Support	5 th	Support (13.43%)	3.23
Visionary Leadership, $\beta_1 = 0,812$ (Third Rank)				
	Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert	IV
1	Futuristic view	1 st	Futuristic view (23.08%)	3.36
2	Clarity of articulating vision	2 nd	Clarity of articulating vision (21.53%)	3.33
3	Direction to achieve success	3 rd	Direction to achieve success (20%)	3.13
4	Encouragement of members to achieve goals	4 th	Encouragement of members to achieve goals (18.47%)	3.27
5	Taking risk with careful calculation	5 th	Taking risk with careful calculation (16.92%)	3.10
Learning Organization, $\beta_2 = 0,784$ (Fourth Rank)				
	Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert	IV
1	Commitment to learning all the time	1 st	Openness to change (20%)	3.48
2	Openness to change	2 nd	Cara berpikir komprehensif dalam memecahkan masalah (17.50%)	3.41
3	Problem-solving approach	3 rd	Problem-solving approach (17.50%)	3.46
4	Members participation in formulating and implementing organizations' vision	4 th	Commitment to learning all the time (16.25%)	3.59
5	Use organizational facilities to collaborate in learning	5 th	Members participation in formulating and implementing organizations' vision (15%)	3.41
6	A comprehensive way of thinking in solving problem	6 th	A comprehensive way of thinking in solving problem (13.75%)	3.60
Creativity, $\beta_3 = 0,851$ (First Rank)				
	Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert	IV
1	The newness of perspective in seeing the situation	1 st	Fluency in generating ideas (23.33%)	3.13
2	The originality of ideas	2 nd	The newness of perspective in seeing the situation (21.67%)	3.10
3	Fluency in generating ideas	3 rd	The originality of ideas (20%)	2.83
4	Flexibility to develop ideas	4 th	Flexibility to develop ideas (18.33%)	3.31
5	Completeness in developing ideas	5 th	Completeness in developing ideas (16.67%)	3.09
Innovative Behavior, $\beta_4 = 0,827$ (Second Rank)				
	Indicator in Initial State		Indicator after Weighting by Expert	IV
1	Exploring new ideas	1 st	Exploring new ideas (23.18%)	3.48
2	Developing new ideas	2 nd	Implementation of the result of the ideas development (21.74%)	2.86
3	Promoting new ideas	3 rd	Developing new ideas (18.84%)	3.18
4	Implementation of the result of the ideas development	4 th	Changes that benefit the organization (18.84%)	3.23
5	Changes that benefit the organization	5 th	Promoting new ideas (17.40%)	2.99

Of the total 26 indicators of the five research variables, only one indicator is feasible to be managed (maintained) and developed, namely teaching (IV = 4.26) as an indicator of lecturer performance. While the other 25 indicators need to be improved (IV < 4.00), namely: flexibility in developing ideas, fluency in generating ideas, the novelty of perspective in viewing situations, completeness in developing ideas, originality of ideas, exploration of new ideas, changes that benefit the organization, development of new ideas, promotion of new ideas, implementation of results, development of ideas, futuristic outlook, clearly articulated vision,

direction to achieve success, encouragement to members to achieve goals, calculated risk-taking, use of organizational facilities to collaborate in learning, commitment to learning over time, openness to change, problem-solving approach, member participation in formulating and implementing the organization's vision, comprehensive way of thinking in solving problems, supporting, community service, research, and scientific publications. This empirical fact shows that the conditions of visionary leadership, learning organizations, creativity, and performance of midwifery university lecturers are still not optimal.

Discussion

This research found that visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative behavior significantly affect lecturers' performance. This finding confirms that visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative behavior are crucial determinants for lecturers' performance. This study indicates that visionary leadership has a direct and significant positive effect on lecturer performance, with an indication of the path coefficient = 0.812 and t value = 15.348 > t table at = 0.01 (2.361). The positive path coefficient value indicates that the improvement of visionary leadership practices can stimulate an increase in lecturer performance. This means that visionary leadership is an important determinant of lecturer performance. Higher education leaders who have a vision for the future will open up insights about future challenges so that they are encouraged to adapt to the various demands of new competencies needed. Lecturers will try to improve their current skills while continuing to hone the new skills needed. This process has an impact on increasing their work results. Visionary leaders encourage lecturers to always be up-to-date in carrying out teaching tasks, research, community service, and scientific publications so that lecturers are motivated to be more productive in conducting research that produces novelties. Leaders who provide examples of how to use the latest information will encourage lecturers to constantly update teaching materials with the latest teaching materials so that the lecture process will run more effectively. Leaders who are able to clearly articulate the university's vision make lecturers feel more confident in the direction of progress that is aspired to by midwifery universities so that they feel that they are given direction to achieve the vision. Leaders who always motivate lecturers to achieve the best results will encourage lecturers to try to carry out the three obligations of higher education optimally so that it helps improve their performance, at least if performance is understood as the result of lecturers' work in completing their duties in accordance with their responsibilities and roles in higher education organizations which include teaching, research, community service, scientific publications, and support. The results of the SITOREM analysis show that the indicator of the leader's futuristic outlook is relatively low, resulting in very limited scientific publications of lecturers as an important component of lecturer performance. The results of research by Widodo and Yusuf (2021), Esfarjani et al. (2020), Setyaningsih et al. (2020), Ali et al. (2019), and Kantabutra (2006) also prove that visionary leadership has an effect on performance. Thus, the results of this study are consistent and confirm the results of previous studies that visionary leadership has an effect on performance in a research setting at midwifery universities lecturers in Banten Province.

The results of this study also show that the learning organization has a direct and significant positive effect on lecturer performance, with an indication of the path coefficient = 0.784 and t value = 13,943 > t table at = 0.01 (2,361). The positive path coefficient value indicates that improving the learning organization can encourage an increase in lecturer performance. In other words, the learning organization is an important antecedent for lecturer performance. A learning organization is an organization where new thinking is constantly valued and fostered. Learning organizations also accommodate the aspirations of individual members, and groups are given freedom. Learning organizations are organizations whose members learn together on an ongoing basis or lifelong learning. Lecturers who constantly improve their skills through learning activities will succeed in carrying out lecture activities more attractively with the new knowledge of their learning outcomes. Lecturers who have a new perspective on the situation have the opportunity to find opportunities or problems that can be turned into useful research activities. Lecturers who have openness and are ready to experiment great opportunities in carrying out research and community service activities that are dynamic by finding problems in the field, so that it shows independence in problem-solving, is able to carry out continuous innovation, and is accustomed to a culture of experimentation, trying new things in both teaching and research. Lecturers who take advantage of the experience of success and failure will be more careful in doing their work so that the quality of their work will increase. Lecturers accustomed to using a systemic way of thinking tend to easily see problems from various perspectives, their interrelationships, and their overall impact. It will help solve problems effectively, facilitating collaboration in research, community service, and other supporting activities. Lecturers passionate about utilizing organizational facilities to study in groups will gain new knowledge from colleagues regarding their roles and duties. From the learning outcomes, lecturers can more easily improve the quality of learning, carry out research and serve the community. This condition will help lecturers to improve their performance as a result of work in completing tasks in accordance with their responsibilities and roles in midwifery universities through teaching, research, community service, scientific publications and support. The results of the SITOREM analysis show that the indicator of openness to change is relatively low, causing lecturers to be less interested in scientific publications. In fact, scientific publications are an important

component for the performance of lecturers in order to support the implementation of the three obligation of Higher Education. Studies conducted by Aziz et al. (2018), Karim and Rahman (2018), Khunsoonthornkit and Panjakajornsak (2018), and Suifan and Allouzi (2018) also prove that learning organizations contribute to performance. If the learning organization is not in good condition, it can hinder the achievement of optimal performance. Thus, the results of this study are the following and confirm the results of previous studies that the learning organization affects performance with the research setting at midwifery universities lecturers in Banten Province.

This study also shows that creativity has a direct and significant positive effect on lecturer performance, indicating of the path coefficient = 0.851 and t value = 17.889 > t table at = 0.01 (2.361). The positive path coefficient value indicates that improvement in creativity can be a stimulant for improving lecturer performance. In other words, creativity is an important determining factor for lecturer performance. Creativity is a deliberate effort to be able to smoothly produce ideas that contain novelty, originality, or the results of the elaboration of previous ideas so that they can be accepted by the work environment, which is reflected in the novelty of perspective in viewing situations, originality of ideas, fluency in generating ideas, flexibility in developing ideas, and completeness in developing the idea. Lecturers who try to find new perspectives when dealing with certain situations will come up with new ideas or ideas that can then be utilized in research. Lecturers who are flexible in developing ideas will easily modify teaching materials into more interesting lecture materials, so they have no trouble replacing old teaching materials with new ones. Lecturers who are flexible in developing ideas are helped in reviewing procedures that need to be improved; their flexibility will make it easier to see opportunities to improve something constant for so long that it becomes a more effective process. Lecturers accustomed to detail in developing ideas will conduct research more carefully, make complete and accurate reports, not quickly satisfied with general ideas. Lecturers who can produce unique and original ideas have the potential to conduct research with high novelty value, which can then be registered to obtain IPR because of the originality of the idea. This condition can potentially spur the performance of lecturers, especially if performance is interpreted as the result of work in completing tasks following their responsibilities and roles in the organization as reflected in teaching, research, community service. The results of the SITOREM analysis show that the fluency indicator in producing lecturers' ideas is relatively low, resulting in a lack of original ideas that can be used for the purposes of writing scientific publications. The research results of Nur et al. (2021), Soegiastuti and Muchayatin (2020), Kaveski and Beuren (2020), and Chandrasekara and Kappagoda (2019) also prove that creativity influences performance. Thus, the results of this study are in line with and confirm the results of previous studies that creativity affects performance with the research setting at midwifery universities lecturers in Banten Province.

This study also shows that innovative behavior has a direct and significant positive effect on lecturer performance, indicating the path coefficient = 0.827 and t value = 16,224 > t table at = 0.01 (2,361). The positive path coefficient value indicates that improving innovative behavior can encourage the improvement of lecturer performance. In other words, innovative behavior is a predisposition of lecturer performance. Innovative behavior is an individual action directed at generating, introducing, or applying new findings in the form of ideas or solutions that benefit the organization, which is reflected in the exploration of new ideas, the realization of new ideas, the development of new ideas, the application of the results of the development of ideas and changes that benefit the organization. Lecturers accustomed to exploring new ideas have a great chance of finding problems which can then make them look for effective solutions. The findings from this exploration can be used as material for research and community service. The findings of the exploration results can also be in the form of new, more efficient ways of doing their work, for example, finding a new format of virtual learning assessment that is more efficient, then this will increase efficiency and effectiveness in teaching. Lecturers who are diligent in developing new ideas can use their ideas into findings that are useful in carrying out their work, for example developing new teaching materials that have a positive impact on increasing student understanding, or developing new models of community service so that the lecturers concerned can collaborate with midwifery universities partners to implement highly efficient community service. Lecturers who are skilled at promoting new ideas will encourage other lecturers to believe and accept their new findings as useful, so they are willing to use them. The use of useful innovation works will have an impact on improving the performance of lecturers. Effective promotion of new ideas will create a more constructive work atmosphere; lecturers will become more aware of the benefits of their colleagues' findings, arouse curiosity, and may stimulate them to carry out innovative activities both in teaching, research, community service, and other supporting activities. This means that behavior that reflects innovation can encourage lecturers' performance, especially if performance is interpreted as the result of work in completing tasks in accordance with their responsibilities and roles in higher education organizations as reflected in teaching, research, community service, scientific publications, and support. The results of the SITOREM analysis of this study show that the indicators for exploring new ideas are relatively low, causing lecturers to be less motivated to do scientific publications. The results of previous research conducted by Marques and Ferreira (2009), Gunday et al. (2011), Schuh et al. (2018), Shanker et al. (2017), Rizki et al. (2019), and Naqvi et al. (2017) also show that innovation has an effect

on performance. Thus, the results of this study are in line with and confirm the results of previous studies that innovative behavior affects performance with the research setting at midwifery universities lecturers in Banten Province.

In addition, the results of this study also show that innovative behavior, besides a direct effect on lecturer performance, is also directly influenced by visionary leadership, with an indication of path coefficient = 0.838 and t value = 16.949 > t table at = 0.01 (2.361). The positive path coefficient value indicates that improvement of visionary leadership practices can stimulate innovative behavior of lecturers. In other words, visionary leadership is an important determinant for the innovative behavior of lecturers. Visionary leadership is a leader behavior that prioritizes the articulation of a clear vision of the future so as to move its members to achieve future success goals, which is reflected in a futuristic view, clarity in articulating the vision, encouragement to members to achieve goals, direction to achieve success and risk-taking with careful calculation. Forward-looking leaders are eager to challenge lecturers to find new opportunities that can be developed and bring benefits to lecturers and universities. Visionary leaders often stimulate members to convey unique ideas about the future so that it makes lecturers try to explore various sources of information to answer leadership challenges. Visionary leaders encourage the achievement of future progress that can be implemented through lecturer innovation activities, lecturers are encouraged to create futuristic-minded teaching materials, utilize the latest knowledge, and even try to create future novelties that direct lecturers to work harder to find new ways to achieve the vision of the future the expected future, both in the form of research, community service and other supporting activities. Leaders who provide clear vision directions to lecturers and try to make it happen, among others, by setting superior standards will encourage lecturers to raise performance standards through findings of more efficient and effective ways of working. Such conditions can trigger innovative behavior of lecturers, namely actions directed at generating, introducing, or applying new findings in the form of ideas or solutions that benefit the organization, which is manifested in exploring new ideas, realizing new ideas, developing new ideas, implementing the results of developing ideas and changing benefit the organization. The results of the SITOREM analysis indicate that the indicator of the leader's futuristic outlook is relatively low, resulting in the limited ability of lecturers to explore new ideas. The results of research by Widodo and Gustari (2020) and Van der Voet and Steijn (2020) also prove that visionary leadership affects innovative behavior. Thus, the results of this study are consistent and confirm the results of previous studies that visionary leadership affects innovative behavior by setting research on lecturers at midwifery universities in Banten Province.

This study also proves that innovative behavior is also directly influenced by the learning organization, indicating the path coefficient = 0.841 and t value = 17.177 > t table at 0.01 (2.361). The positive path coefficient value indicates that improving the learning organization can encourage innovative behavior of lecturers. In other words, the learning organization is a determining factor for the innovative behavior of lecturers. A learning organization is an organization where its members continuously expand their capacity based on a shared vision to create the desired results by nurturing new thinking and expansion patterns, collective aspirations, and systemic thinking, which is reflected in a commitment to learning over time, openness to change, formulating and apply organizational vision, use organizational facilities to collaborate in learning, and comprehensive way of thinking in solving problems. Midwifery universities that are concerned with lifelong learning activities tend to encourage every potential institution, especially lecturers, to continuously improve their competence and skills. This achievement can be done through the exploration of development opportunities. In the exploration process, lecturers have the opportunity to find new ideas that are beneficial to them or the organization. Midwifery Universities that provide facilitation for lecturers to study in teams will open up opportunities for collaboration between lecturers, brainstorming, giving each other input so that it is likely to produce new findings that can be jointly developed by lecturers. Midwifery Universities that show openness to change will open discussions with lecturers to evaluate ongoing educational processes. This forum is an opportunity for new findings to occur, for example, new ways to conduct student assessments that are more effective, new topics of useful research, new collaborations in community service. Midwifery Universities who are accustomed to using a comprehensive and systemic approach in dealing with problems will try to find solutions that are as effective as possible considering all aspects; this will help lecturers develop new ideas, practice taking into account all components in developing new ideas so that they will increase their usefulness. In summary, learning organizations can stimulate the emergence of innovative behavior of lecturers, namely individual actions directed at generating, introducing, or applying new findings in the form of ideas or solutions that benefit the organization, which is manifested in exploring new ideas, realizing new ideas, developing new ideas, implementing the results of developing ideas and changes that benefit the organization. The results of the SITOREM analysis show that the indicator of openness to change is relatively low, which makes lecturers less interested in exploring new ideas. The research results of Allouzi et al. (2018), Anwar and Niode (2017), Park et al. (2016), and Chen et al. (2018) also show that learning organizations have a significant relationship with innovative behavior. Thus, the results of this study are in accordance with and confirm the results of previous studies that learning organizations have an effect on innovative behavior by setting research on lecturers at midwifery universities in Banten Province.

This study also proves that creativity has a direct positive effect on innovative behavior, indicating the path coefficient = 0.937, with t value = 29.699 > t table at = 0.01 (2.361). The positive path coefficient value indicates that the improvement of creativity can trigger the growth of lecturers' innovative behavior. In other words, creativity is a predisposition for the innovative behavior of lecturers. Creativity is a deliberate effort to be able to smoothly produce ideas that contain novelty, originality, or the results of the elaboration of previous ideas so that they can be accepted by the work environment, which is reflected in the novelty of perspective in viewing situations, originality of ideas, fluency in generating ideas, flexibility in developing ideas, and completeness in developing an idea. Lecturers who try to use a new perspective in seeing a situation will automatically explore the various knowledge needed so that when compiling their perspective, there is a great opportunity to find ideas that have never been thought of before. Lecturers who try to find original ideas tend to be prepared to answer other lecturers' doubts about their new ideas, so they try to promote their ideas by showing the benefits of their ideas, the practicality of using their ideas, and especially the impact of their original ideas on their colleagues. Lecturers who come up with new ideas will try to elaborate on their ideas, so they ask for input from their colleagues through testing ideas, and this can further increase the activity of implementing their new findings, which then try to make models for their colleagues to test and evaluate. This means that creativity is an antecedent for the innovative behavior of lecturers. The results of the SITOREM analysis show that the indicator of fluency in generating lecturers' ideas is relatively low, resulting in the limited ability of lecturers to explore new ideas. Research conducted by Suendarti et al. (2020) and Slåtten (2014) also proves that creativity has a significant effect on innovative behavior. Thus, the results of this study are consistent with and confirm the results of previous studies that creativity has an effect on innovative behavior with the research setting at midwifery universities in Banten Province.

In addition, the results of this study also prove that visionary leadership has an indirect effect on lecturer performance through innovative behavior, with an indication of the path coefficient = 0.693 and Z value = 11.80 > Z table at the significant level = 0.01 (2.576). The positive path coefficient value indicates that improvement in the practice of visionary leadership at midwifery universities can trigger the growth of lecturers' innovative behavior and then have implications for lecturers' performance. The condition shows a significant role of innovative behavior in mediating the influence of visionary leadership on lecturer performance. In reality, the leadership of midwifery universities who are skilled in articulating the conditions of the future that are aspired to will illustrate the need for innovation to achieve the conditions that are aspired to together. Such leaders will open up opportunities for discussion with members of midwifery universities to explore various possibilities to achieve their vision. In the exploration process, lecturers are challenged to find new knowledge as a bridge to achieve the vision, which then the findings can be developed into new useful ideas. For example, the leadership of midwifery universities who want graduates who are competitive at the global level will encourage lecturers to find effective learning methods to produce students to achieve the desired competencies. In this case, the lecturer will collect superior lecture standards then plan new breakthroughs in lectures. It will make him more proficient in compiling global standard RPS, spurring him to find new teaching methods so that the quality of his teaching increases. In the process, lecturers are encouraged to design lecture programs that are effective but still efficient so that, overall, these new findings will result in superior lecturer performance. Visionary leaders will also be pioneers and examples in carrying out activities to achieve the vision in the future. This action will encourage lecturers to imitate it so that they actively participate in finding effective ways to achieve the futuristic vision of universities. The results of the SITOREM analysis of this study indicate that the indicators of the leadership's futuristic outlook are relatively lacking, resulting in a relatively limited ability of lecturers to explore new ideas and then causing a lack of interest for lecturers to carry out scientific publication activities. Thus, this finding is in line with the findings of the direct influence of visionary leadership on innovative behavior and innovative behavior towards lecturers and confirms the results of previous research conducted by Widodo and Gustari (2020) and Van der Voet and Steijn (2020), which proves that visionary leadership effect on innovative behavior and the study of Schuh et al. (2018), Shanker et al. (2017), Rizki et al. (2019) and Naqvi et al. (2017) which shows that innovative behavior affects performance in a research setting at midwifery universities lecturers in Banten Province.

The results of this study also show that learning organizations have an indirect effect on lecturer performance by mediating innovative behavior, with an indication of the path coefficient = 0.696 and Z value = 11.78 > Z table at the significant level = 0.01 (2.576). The positive path coefficient value indicates that improving the learning organization of midwifery universities can stimulate innovative behavior of lecturers and then have implications for lecturer performance. The condition shows the significant role of innovative behavior in mediating the influence of the learning organization on lecturer performance. A learning organization is an organization where its members continuously expand their capacity based on a shared vision to create the desired results by nurturing new thinking and expansion patterns, collective aspirations, and systemic thinking, which is reflected in a commitment to learning over time, openness to change, a solution approach problems, the participation of members in formulating and implementing the organization's vision, the use of organizational facilities to collaborate in learning, and a comprehensive way of thinking in solving problems. In practice, when

an organization facilitates its members to continuously expand their capacity to create the results they want, there are opportunities to generate innovations in various activities. In the learning organization, new thoughts and patterns of expansion are maintained so that members are stimulated to seek novelty, new ways, new procedures, new products that will bring benefits to the organization. It will increase innovation among members. New findings that are useful will then be applied in work activities or operations. The application of these new findings will contribute to the quality and quantity of work. Innovation in work procedures, for example, will make members more efficient in carrying out their duties. Commitment to learning over time will increase the skills of organizational members in the learning process coupled with efforts to use new perspectives in looking at problems, making members motivated to find new things. Improving members' skills through continuous learning will make them need higher standards that encourage them to make new discoveries. In the end, increased skills accompanied by new findings will contribute significantly to the quality of work. The results of the SITOREM analysis show that the indicator of openness to change is relatively low, resulting in the ability of lecturers to explore new ideas is relatively limited, and this has implications for lecturers' lack of interest in scientific publication activities. Thus, this finding is in line with the findings of the direct influence of learning organizations on innovative behavior and innovative behavior towards lecturers and confirms the results of previous research conducted by, among others, Allouzi et al. (2018), Anwar and Niode (2017), Park et al. (2016) and Chen et al. (2018) that learning organizations have a significant relationship with innovative behavior and the study of Schuh et al. (2018), Shanker et al. (2017), Rizki et al. (2019) and Naqvi et al. (2017) which shows that innovative behavior affects performance in a research setting at midwifery universities lecturers in Banten Province.

This study also shows that creativity has an indirect effect on lecturer performance by mediating innovative behavior, with an indication of the path coefficient = 0.778 and $Z_{value} = 14.28 > Z_{table}$ at the significant level = 0.01 (2.576). The positive path coefficient value indicates that improvement in creativity can stimulate innovative behavior of lecturers and then have implications for improving lecturer performance. The condition shows the important role of innovative behavior in mediating the effect of creativity on lecturer performance. Creativity is a deliberate effort to be able to smoothly produce ideas that contain novelty, originality or the results of the elaboration of previous ideas so that they can be accepted by the work environment, which is reflected in the novelty of perspective in viewing situations, originality of ideas, fluency in generating ideas, flexibility in developing ideas, completeness in developing ideas. In reality, creative lecturers will show efforts to produce unique, new ideas or modifications of old ideas. The idea will be sought to be a useful finding for himself, the group, and the organization. In order to become an effective product, lecturers need to elaborate ideas, compare, improve, make details, and try out. This creative and innovative process trains lecturers' thinking power, critical thinking, trained lecturers to see various perspectives of a phenomenon. This activity can be applied by lecturers in various tasks, for example, in research and service. Creative and innovative activities encourage lecturers to reveal the strengths and weaknesses of an idea; this indirectly increases their competence which then has the potential to have a positive impact on their performance. The results of the SITOREM analysis indicate that the indicator of fluency in generating lecturers' ideas is relatively low, resulting in the limited ability of lecturers to explore new ideas and then the implications for lecturers' lack of interest in scientific publication activities. Thus, this finding is in line with the finding of a direct effect of creativity on innovative behavior and innovative behavior on lecturers and confirms the results of previous research conducted by, among others, Suendarti et al. (2020) and Slåtten (2014), which prove that creativity has a significant effect on innovative behavior and the study of Schuh et al. (2018), Shanker et al. (2017), Rizki et al. (2019), and Naqvi et al. (2017) which shows that innovative behavior affects performance in a research setting at midwifery universities lecturers in Banten Province.

Overall, this study found a new model as a novelty, namely a model of the influence of visionary leadership, learning organizations, and creativity on lecturer performance by mediating innovative behavior with research settings at midwifery universities lecturers in Banten Province. Naturally, this finding can be used as a topic for discussion among researchers and practitioners. Furthermore, it can also be adopted as a model for developing lecturers' performance through visionary leadership, creativity, and innovative behavior across various locations, sectors, organizations, and contexts.

Conclusion

The study explores the empirical effect of visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work on lecturers' performance, but also to prove the theoretical model regarding innovative behavior as a mediator of visionary leadership, learning organization and creativity on lecturers' performance. The research found that visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work have a significant effect on lecturers' performance. Besides, innovative behavior also indirectly mediates the effect of visionary leadership, learning organization, and creativity on lecturers' performance. Thus, a new model regarding the effect of visionary leadership, learning organization, and creativity on lecturers' performance, mediated by innovative work, was confirmed. The research suggested that the lecturers' performance can

improve through visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work. Therefore, researchers and practitioners can adopt a new empirical model to enhance lecturers' performance through visionary leadership, learning organization, creativity, and innovative work in the future.

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